

Contribution of The Mysore Province to Literary Translation works in Kannada and English Language

Prasad N.

Assistant Professor, Department of English, Govt. First Grade College, K.R. Sagara,
Srirangapatna, Mandya.

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ABSTRACT:

The Mysore Province which was a seat of excellence greatly benefited by the establishment of the Oriental Library, at Mysore in 1891. The Literary translations from other languages to Kannada and vice versa, gained momentum from then and helped the Kannada literary arena, to flourish and bloom into a full-fledged expressive and inclusive modern language. The translations gave a host of novel and fresh literary forms and ideas, which joined forces with the grand repository of existing classic literature. Many literary personalities starting from B M Sri to A K Ramanujan, contributed to the enrichment of Kannada language through their deft translation works. The paper speaks about the contribution of Mysore province for such translatory works, lists out them and their impact on Kannada literature.

KEYWORDS:

Oriental, Occidental, Wodeyar, Translation, Verse, Samsthana.

Ever since the establishment of the oriental library in 1891 by his highness Sri Chamaraja Wodeyar Bahadur, the Maharaja of Mysore Samsthana, the literary activities gathered wings in terms of preservation of existing classic Indian literature and outcome of fresh and contemporary forms and thoughts. A library consisting of literature, culture and co-related works were given a great impetus to the progress of literary activities in Mysore. Thus, the Mysore province indeed acted as a depository of Indian literature as well as a bastion of synthesis of both, the oriental and occidental literature, organically becoming the abode of literary and cultural prog-

ress of Southern India. The origin of voicing the downtrodden and the deprived class, emanated from the Mysore Province, then anywhere else in India, under the stewardship of the Wodeyar dynasty.

B M Srikantaiah (1884-1946) translated English poems into 'English Geethegalu' which introduced Free Verse writing style to Kannada. He translated Sophocles' Ajax to Kannada by the name of Ashwathaman. Parasikaru is another translation, in addition to another work, 'Islam Sanskriti' into Kannada. The Mysore Maharaja granted him the title 'Raja Seva Sakta'. Renowned poet M S Putanna (1854-1930) translated Shakespeare's Cymbelene as Simharaja Charita in Kannada. King Lear as Hemachandra Raja Vilasa. He was one of the founders of Kannada Sahitya Parishad. B venkatacharya (1845-1914) who was born in Mandya District translated Bengali works of Vidyasagar's Bhranti vilas into Kannada. He translated Shakespeare's Merchant of Venice to Venice Nagara Vanika. A R Krishna Shastrri (1890-1968) who was born in Mysore, translated Nagamahayasa from Bengali. Basavappa Shastrri, (1843-91) who is renowned as 'modern Kalidasa', translated Shakespeare's Othello as Shurasena charita. Another literary personality, Srikanthesh Gowda A L (1852-1926) was born in Maddur Taluk, translated many books to Kannada. He translated Shakespeare's Othello, A Midsummer Night's dream and Romeo and Juliet as Prataparudra Deva, Pramilarjuniyam and Ramavarma Lilavathi respectively. S G Narasimha Achar (1862-1907) who was born in Srirangapatna, had mastery over Tamil and English language. He translated certain verses of Raghuvamsha of Kalidasa, besides translating many English rhymes into Kannada like Twinkle Twinkle Little Star, along with translations of Aesop's Fables, Gulliver's Travels, The Taming of the Shrew, to Kannada. Maṣṭi Venkatesh Iyengar (1891-1986), a Jnanapeet awardee, translated Shakespeare's Tempest as Chandamaruta, Twelfth Night as Dvadasha Ratri, King Lear as Lear Maharaja to Kannada. A N Murthy Rao (1900-2003) translated Moliere's plays. He also translated Sivaramakaram Karantha's book as Return to the soil to English. K S Narasimha Swamy (1915-2003) translated Hucklebury Finn's Adventures and Media into Kannada. Ajjampura Sitaram (1902-1963), pennamed as Ananda, translated Defoe's Robinson Crusoe, Stevenson's Treasure Island, Leo Tolstoy's The Ordeal

and Sir Walter Scott's *Ivanhoe* into Kannada. Dejavare Gowda (1915-2016), translated Tolstoy's *War and Peace*, *Resurrection* and *Anna Karenina*, Jane Austin's *Pride and Prejudice* into Kannada. Ka.Vem. Raghavachar (1904-77), was born in below translated settled plays from Greek by the name movie part of the low which consists of *Antigone* of Sophocles, *Agamemnon*, *Oedipus king Rex*, *The frogs* as Mooru Greek Natakagalu in addition to translating Aristotle's *Poetics*. Thus, we can observe Kannada language being profusely supplied with new concepts of literary imagination and various forms of artistic expression. We can also see many kannada and Sanskrit works being translated to English, a mutual space for growth and understanding being created with this translational movement.

Mysore princely state was a prestigious region in the cultural history of India which achieved remarkable distinction in terms of statesmanship and artistic excellence. It should be noted that the British influence might have contributed a great deal of incognito inspiration, drawn from the renowned English literary works which went on to be infused into Kannada literary tradition, thus enriching the Kannada literary movement further. The zeal to match the audacity of English literature, encouraged a flurry of translations to and from Kannada. Besides the influence of Sanskrit and other vernacular languages, these translations infused a sense of contemporary and an influx of fresh ideas to Kannada literature, not to mention the unflinching patronage of Mysore wideners who themselves were great scholars, besides aiding literary and allied art forms. As a result, both Kannada and English literary fields flourished in a great way, creating new branches of productivity, which had a lasting impact on imagining a multi-hued, diverse and inclusive literary genre.

Reference:

1. Rajappa Dalawayi. (2018). Kannada Sahitya Kosha. Dr. Rajappa Dalawayi Tarabethi Kendra. Bengaluru.

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